

Resolving the Apparent Paradoxes of Special Relativity

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(Dated: October 27, 2025)

Since its formulation by Albert Einstein in 1905, the theory of Special Relativity has completely altered our classical understanding of space, time, and simultaneity. The theory's postulates lead to a series of counterintuitive consequences, such as time dilation, length contraction, and the relativity of simultaneity, which have given rise to numerous so-called paradoxes, or **Gedankenexperiments**, which seem to expose logical contradictions within the theory. This paper provides a detailed conceptual analysis of three of the most famous of these thought experiments. Each scenario will be formally presented and examined in a dedicated section. By rigorously applying the principles and mathematical tools of the theory, this paper resolves each apparent contradiction.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. Historical background

For over two centuries, the laws of motion established by Isaac Newton provided a seemingly complete and intuitive description of the world. This classical framework was built on a foundation that was considered self-evident: the idea that space is fixed and that time flows at the same rate for every observer, everywhere.

However, by the end of the 19th century, this stable picture began to reveal significant inconsistencies. James Clerk Maxwell's theory of electromagnetism accurately describes light as an electromagnetic wave, but the most surprising discovery is that the speed of light depends on universal constants, the permittivity and permeability of free space ($c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}}$), and therefore must be the same for all observers. This directly conflicted with the classical view that velocity is relative and depends on the observer's RF. To solve this, scientists proposed a "**luminiferous aether**", an invisible, all-pervading medium through which light must travel at speed c .

This idea was famously put to the test in the **Michelson-Morley experiment** [1, p. 18-26]. The experiment was designed to detect the "aether wind", the difference in light's speed due to Earth's motion through the aether, but it found nothing. The speed of light was the same in all directions.

In this context of crisis, **Albert Einstein** published his **theory of Special Relativity** in 1905, exactly 120 years ago[2]. Einstein's approach was revolutionary. He abandoned the aether entirely and, more radically, the concepts of absolute space and absolute time. He built his entire theory on **two simple postulates**:

- The laws of physics are invariant in all inertial frames of reference (that is, frames of reference with no acceleration). This is known as the **principle of relativity**.
- The speed of light in vacuum is the same for all observers, regardless of the motion of light source or observer. This is known as the **principle of**

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light speed invariance.

All this resulted in redefining space and time[1, p. 1-38]. In Einstein's framework, space and time are no longer absolute but **interdependent and flexible**. From that moment on, concepts such as **time dilation** and **length contraction** became actual physical realities. Moreover, two events that appear 'simultaneous' to one observer may not be to another (**relativity of simultaneity**).

These consequences were so profoundly counterintuitive that, from the very start, the theory was met with significant skepticism and criticism[3].

B. Physical and mathematical concepts of SR

1. Lorentz transformations

FIG. 1: Schematic representation of two reference frames: the fixed frame O and the moving frame O' , showing the apparent displacement of a light beam according to Galilean transformations. Image adapted from Appunti di Relatività Speciale(Teoria) [4, p. 58]

It is immediately evident that Galileo's transformations are incompatible with the second postulate[4, p. 59]. In fact, let's imagine a light beam in the moving reference frame O' (which is moving at velocity v in the same direction as the beam), beginning to propagate(Figure 1).

If for O' the light travels at c , for O it is different, because we must take into account that the reference frame O' has moved.

According to the velocity addition of Galileo's transformations, in the fixed reference frame, the beam has a velocity $w = (c+v)$, which violates the second postulate, according to which the speed of light is constant in all reference frames.

It is therefore necessary to introduce new transformations that are capable of respecting the two postulates of SR. **Hendrik Lorentz** played a central role in formulating the mathematical framework of the theory. Working on electron theory, Lorentz sought to develop a theory that would make Maxwell's equations invariant when moving from one reference frame (the stationary ether) to another (a moving electron) [5, p. 13]. On the other hand, it is Einstein who is able to give a physical meaning to what the transformations show, using them as a mathematical foundation for his theory.

Given a stationary reference frame S and a frame S' moving with a constant velocity v along the $+x$ axis relative to S , the coordinates in S' are related to the coordinates in S by the **Lorentz transformations**:

$$\begin{cases} x' = \gamma(x - vt) \\ y' = y \\ z' = z \\ t' = \gamma\left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where γ is the **Lorentz factor**, defined as:

$$\gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

To obtain the Lorentz transformations from S' to S , it is necessary to reverse the sign of the velocity.

If interested in the derivation, see Appendix(VI A).

The Lorentz transformations can also be expressed in a more compact matrix form. By defining the spacetime 4-vectors $\vec{x} = (ct, x, y, z)^T$, the transformation $\vec{x}' = \Lambda \vec{x}$ is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} ct' \\ x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\gamma\beta & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} ct \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$ and γ is the Lorentz factor previously defined in Eq. (2). The matrix form explicitly shows the mixing of time and space coordinates along the direction of motion, reflecting the inseparability of space and time in Special Relativity.

2. Minkowski spacetime

In 1908, with the famous conference held in Köln, which went down in history as "**Raum und Zeit**" (Space and Time), Minkowski introduced the concept of **four-dimensional spacetime**, thereby providing a new geometric and mathematical formulation of special relativity.

"From now on, space alone and time alone are destined to vanish like mere shadows, and only their union will preserve an independent existence." This sentence, pronounced by him, describes the new vision of physical reality [6, p. 8].

It can be easily demonstrated that the Lorentz transformations of the space-time coordinates of physical events preserve the **spacetime interval** s^2 . For an event's coordinates (t, x, y, z) relative to the origin, this interval is defined by the quadratic form:

$$s^2 = c^2t^2 - x^2 - y^2 - z^2 = c^2t'^2 - x'^2 - y'^2 - z'^2 = s'^2$$

This invariance suggested to Minkowski that Lorentz transformations could be thought of as **rotations** in this

four-dimensional space. This space is characterized by the **Minkowski metric** $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ (a pseudo-Euclidean metric), which in this convention is

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In Minkowski spacetime, every physical event is represented by a point in a four-dimensional vector space, described by a **position four-vector**. In contravariant form it is written as:

$$x^\mu = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) = (ct, x, y, z),$$

where the index $\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$ labels the time and spatial components. The corresponding covariant components are obtained by lowering the index using the Minkowski metric (signature $+, -, -, -$):

$$x_\mu = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\nu = (ct, -x, -y, -z).$$

A Lorentz transformation is represented by a 4×4 matrix, Λ . This matrix is defined by the property that it preserves the Minkowski metric (i.e., $\Lambda^T \eta \Lambda = \eta$) and has a determinant of $\det(\Lambda) = \pm 1$.

The relationship between the four-vector components in one frame (x^ν) and another frame (x'^μ) is expressed using Einstein's summation convention([VIB1](#)) as:

$$x'^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu x^\nu$$

The Minkowski metric allows raising and lowering indices[[7](#), p. 92]:

$$x_\mu = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\nu, \quad x^\mu = \eta^{\mu\nu} x_\nu, \quad (4)$$

where $\eta^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor (identical to $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ in this convention).

The spacetime interval can therefore be expressed in a compact and invariant form as:

$$s^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\mu x^\nu. \quad (5)$$

Under a Lorentz transformation, since $\Lambda^T \eta \Lambda = \eta$, the interval remains invariant:

$$s'^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} x'^\mu x'^\nu = \eta_{ps} x^p x^s = s^2. \quad (6)$$

This invariance is the geometric foundation of all relativistic effects.

For the mathematical formalism see the Appendix([VIB2](#)).

Another important concept is the fact that a Lorentz boost can thus be interpreted as a **hyperbolic rotation** in spacetime[[8](#), p. 1]. For a boost along the x -axis with velocity v ,

$$\begin{pmatrix} ct' \\ x' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh \phi & -\sinh \phi \\ -\sinh \phi & \cosh \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} ct \\ x \end{pmatrix},$$

where the rapidity ϕ is defined by $\tanh \phi = v/c$. The Lorentz factor is then $\gamma = \cosh \phi$ and $\beta\gamma = \sinh \phi$. This representation makes explicit that Lorentz transformations preserve the spacetime interval in the same way that ordinary rotations preserve spatial distances. See the Appendix([VIC](#)) for more details.

The **scalar (inner) product** between two four-vectors,

$$\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y} = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\mu y^\nu,$$

is invariant under Lorentz transformations. For example, for the four-position vector x^μ , the invariant scalar is precisely the spacetime interval $s^2 = \vec{x} \cdot \vec{x}$.

Depending on the sign of the spacetime interval, four-vectors can be classified as:

$$\begin{cases} s^2 > 0 & \text{time-like,} \\ s^2 = 0 & \text{light-like (null),} \\ s^2 < 0 & \text{space-like.} \end{cases}$$

Events can only be **causally connected** if their interval is time-like or light-like ($s^2 \geq 0$). Space-like separated events ($s^2 < 0$) cannot be causally connected.

For an even more detailed mathematical study, see Appendix([VID](#)).

This geometric structure of spacetime provides the foundation for understanding the physical consequences of Special Relativity, such as time dilation, length contraction, and the relativity of simultaneity, which can be elegantly represented in Minkowski diagrams.

3. Physical consequences and visualization

Having introduced the fundamental mathematical tools behind the theory, it is now possible to analyze some counterintuitive aspects from a physical point of view.

From the 4th equation of Lorentz transformations, defined in Eq. (1), it is possible to notice how time and space are closely connected to each other. Time dilation is a consequence of this.

Consider a clock stationary at the origin of the moving reference frame S' . The Minkowski diagram([Figure 2](#)) immediately shows that S sees a clock in motion with the same velocity as S' , which, however, measures time differently.[[4](#), p. 120]

In fact, this fact can be expressed mathematically with the following equation:

$$\Delta x'^0 \vec{e}_0 = \Delta x^0 \vec{e}_0 + \Delta x^1 \vec{e}_1$$

To obtain the time interval measured by S , it is multiplied by the unit vector \vec{e}_0 :

$$\Delta x'^0 \vec{e}_0 \cdot \vec{e}_0 = \Delta x^0 \vec{e}_0 \cdot \vec{e}_0 + \Delta x^1 \vec{e}_1 \cdot \vec{e}_0$$

Taking into account that:

$$\vec{e}_j \cdot \vec{e}_k = \eta_{jk} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{e}'_j \cdot \vec{e}_k = \eta_{jp} (\Lambda_k^p)^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & \gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma\beta & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where η_{jk} is the Minkowski metric and δ_{jk} the Kronecker delta, the following relationship is obtained by swapping the order of the indices (using the symmetry of η):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x'^0 \gamma &= \Delta x^0 \implies \Delta x^0 = \frac{\Delta x'^0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \\ \implies \Delta t &= \frac{\Delta t'}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Which shows how time flows for the stationary reference system knowing the time interval of S' and the relative translation speed.

FIG. 2: Minkowski diagram with inertial reference frames S and S' . The coordinates with 0 represent the temporal component, those with 1 the spatial component. The phenomenon of time dilation can be observed.

Closely related to time dilation is spatial contraction, a phenomenon that is also very counterintuitive. Minkowski diagrams make the discussion more understandable and logical.

Consider a bar of length L_0 at rest in the moving reference frame O' , with one end at the origin and the other along the x' axis. From the Minkowski diagram (Figure 3), it can be seen that the length measured by S , which is defined as the distance between two observers of S who see the ends of the rod at the same instant, will be shorter. [4, p. 122]

The length measured by S , L_m , must be the projection of L_0 on \vec{e}_1 , removing the temporal part determined by b .

From the figure, the following relationships are also obtained:

$$L_0 \vec{e}'_1 = (b + L_m) \vec{e}_1 + c \vec{e}_0 \quad a \vec{e}'_0 = c \vec{e}_0 + b \vec{e}_1$$

Multiplying by the 2 unit vectors of S :

$$L_0 \vec{e}'_1 \vec{e}_0 = (b + L_m) \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_0 + c \vec{e}_0 \vec{e}_0 \quad a \vec{e}'_0 \vec{e}_0 = c \vec{e}_0 \vec{e}_0 + b \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_0$$

$$L_0 \vec{e}'_1 \vec{e}_1 = (b + L_m) \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1 + c \vec{e}_0 \vec{e}_1 \quad a \vec{e}'_0 \vec{e}_1 = c \vec{e}_0 \vec{e}_0 + b \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1$$

And using Eq. (7) and Eq. (8):

$$L_0 \beta \gamma = c \quad a \gamma = c$$

$$L_0 \gamma = (b + L_m) \quad a \gamma \beta = b$$

Leads to:

$$(b + L_m) = L_0 \gamma \quad b = L_0 \beta^2 \gamma$$

The final result is:

$$L_m = L_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (10)$$

Which clearly shows the contraction of lengths.

FIG. 3: Minkowski diagram with inertial reference frames S and S' . The coordinates with 0 represent the temporal component, those with 1 the spatial component. The phenomenon of length contraction can be observed.

In this section, the last topic that will be addressed is the relativity of simultaneity [4, p. 121]. Consider two events occur simultaneously in S' , the time interval measured by S will be different from 0. From the chart (Figure 4), it can be seen that:

$$\Delta x'^1 \vec{e}'_1 = \Delta x^0 \vec{e}_0 + \Delta x^1 \vec{e}_1$$

To obtain the time interval measured by S , it is necessary to multiply by the unit vector \vec{e}_0 , and using Eq.(7) and Eq.(8):

$$\Delta x'^1 \vec{e}'_1 \vec{e}_0 = \Delta x^0 \vec{e}_0 \vec{e}_0 + \Delta x^1 \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_0 \implies \Delta x'^1 \beta \gamma = \Delta x^0$$

To highlight the relativity of simultaneity, the result can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta t = \Delta x' \frac{\frac{v}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (11)$$

Now it is possible to carry out a detailed analysis of the most well-known thought experiments.

FIG. 4: Minkowski diagram with inertial reference frames S and S' . The coordinates with 0 represent the temporal component, those with 1 the spatial component. The phenomenon of relativity of simultaneity can be observed.

II. THE TWIN PARADOX

A. Description

The **twin paradox** is certainly one of the most well-known thought experiments, even among those outside the field of physics.

Imagine two twin brothers, Andrew and Barney. The first stays on Earth, while the second decides to embark on a stellar journey, moving at speeds close to that of light. Due to time dilation, a concept introduced in previous paragraphs, the brother who is moving should be younger upon his return. But here arises the paradox: according to the principle of relativity, from his frame of reference, Barney can say that it is Andrew who is moving, and therefore it is Andrew who should be younger. How is this contradiction resolved?

The key lies in the fact that there is a **break in the symmetry** of the problem. Two solutions will be proposed, involving **proper time**[1, p. 202] and the **relativistic Doppler effect**[1, p. 205].

FIG. 5: Minkowski diagram showing two different paths, representing proper time, connecting 2 points in space-time.

B. Analysis 1

It is necessary to explain what proper time is and how to calculate it in order to understand its usefulness.

The proper time of a reference frame is defined as the time measured by clocks at rest in the given reference frame[9, p. 34]. Using Eq.(6) and rewriting it in differential form:

$$c^2 dt'^2 - d\vec{x}'^2 = c^2 dt^2 - d\vec{x}^2$$

From the moving frame of reference, $d\vec{x}' = 0$ using the definition. This implies:

$$c^2 dt'^2 = c^2 dt^2 - d\vec{x}^2 \implies dt' = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{d\vec{x}^2}{c^2 dt^2}}$$

$$\implies dt' = dt \sqrt{1 - \frac{v(t)^2}{c^2}}$$

Now, it is possible to calculate the proper time of the two paths in the diagram(Figure 5)[1, p. 202]. For Δt , $dx = 0$:

$$\Delta t = \int_{t_P}^{t_Q} \sqrt{dt^2 - \frac{dx^2}{c^2}} \implies \int_{t_P}^{t_Q} dt$$

$$\Delta t = t_Q - t_P$$

For $\Delta t'$:

$$\Delta t' = \int_{t_P}^{t_Q} \sqrt{dt^2 - \frac{dx^2}{c^2}}$$

And since $\frac{dx^2}{c^2} > 0$:

$$\implies \Delta t > \Delta t'$$

This demonstrates that the world lines of the inertially moving bodies (Δt - Andrew) maximize the proper time elapsed between two events, thus showing that Barney, who in his journey must accelerate, decelerate, and change course, is the twin who will have aged less.

C. Analysis 2

In this section, the problem will be solved using the relativistic Doppler effect (VIE), neglecting the effects of acceleration and deceleration, thus considering Barney in two different inertial reference frames.

Let the spaceship be equipped with identical clocks which send out light signals at one-year intervals. Andrew receives the signals arriving from Barney's clock and records them against the annual signals of his own clock; likewise, Barney receives the signals from Andrew's clock and records them against the annual signals of his clock [1, p. 205].

Suppose the spaceship has a constant speed (v) of $0.6c$ and the journey lasts 10 years as measured from Earth (Δt). The frequency of clock-ticks which one sees from a source with rest frequency f_r , when the source is moving directly away, is:

$$f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v}{c}}}$$

By entering the data used in this example:

$$f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{1 - 0.6}{1 + 0.6}} \implies f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{0.4}{1.6}}$$

$$f_{obs} = \frac{1}{2} f_r$$

Hence, Andrew receives the first signal from Barney after two of his years. Similarly, Barney receives messages from Andrew on the way out once every two of his years. Since his outbound journey lasts 4 years (Barney's time), he receives a total of two signals during this phase.

After 5 years measured by Andrew, the spacecraft reverses course and begins to return to Earth.

The frequency of clock-ticks observed from a source with rest frequency f_r , when the source is moving directly towards, is:

$$f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}}$$

By entering the data used in this example:

$$f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{1 + 0.6}{1 - 0.6}} \implies f_{obs} = f_r \sqrt{\frac{1.6}{0.4}}$$

$$f_{obs} = 2f_r$$

Thus, Andrew observes this blueshifted signal for the last 2 years of the journey. At this double frequency, he receives 4 signals.

Altogether, Andrew receives 8 signals (4 during the 8-year redshift phase, and 4 during the 2-year blueshift phase).

Similarly, Barney observes the blueshifted signal from Earth for his entire 4-year return journey. He receives 8 signals during this phase. Altogether, Barney receives 10 signals (2 during his 4-year outbound phase, and 8 during his 4-year return phase).

There is no disagreement about the signals: Andrew sends 10 and receives 8. Barney sends 8 and receives 10. Both agree that Andrew has aged 10 years while Barney has aged only 8.

The chart (Figure 6) shows the sending and receiving of various signals from the two perspectives of the twins.

FIG. 6: Signal exchange pattern between the twins. The code used to generate this figure is available in the supplementary material. [10]

III. MUON DECAY

A. Description

Muons are subatomic particles that form when cosmic rays interact with the upper atmosphere. Due to their short lifetimes measured in the laboratory, it was believed that no particle could reach the Earth's surface. Using a Geiger-Müller counter, Rossi and Hall found that many more muons reached the ground than classically predicted [11, p. 223]. The result is perfectly explained by the concepts of **time dilation** and **length contraction**.

(a) Reference frame of the Earth. The distance is L_0 , but the muon μ is time-dilated ($\Delta t = \gamma\tau_\mu$).

(b) Reference frame of the Muon. The lifetime is τ_μ , but the distance L_0 is contracted ($L = \frac{L_0}{\gamma}$).

FIG. 7: Comparison between the two reference systems (Earth and Muon).

B. Analysis

The lifetime of the muon[12] measured in the laboratory is:

$$\tau_\mu = (2.1969811 \pm 0.0000022) \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$$

For the calculations, the value of $\tau_\mu = 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$ will be used. Furthermore, they move at extremely high velocities ($v = 0.9999c$)[13, p. 1]. They are created at about 10 km above sea level ($L_0 = 10 \text{ km}$), therefore, through a classical analysis of the problem ($d_t = v \times \tau_\mu = 600 \text{ m}$), it would appear that they cannot reach the ground.

Through Eq.(9):

$$\Delta t = \frac{2.2 \times 10^{-6}}{\sqrt{1 - (0.9999)^2}} \implies \Delta t = 156 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$$

Using this time interval, the distance traveled by the muon is $d_m = v \times \Delta t = 47 \text{ km}$, which is greater than 10 km , implying that the muon reaches the ground(Figure 7a). It is also possible to use length contraction.

Through Eq.(10):

$$L = L_0 \sqrt{1 - (0.9999)^2} \implies L = 141 \text{ m}$$

The shortened distance that the muon has to travel is 141 m , less than 600 m , so it will reach the ground(Figure 7b).

This shows that both approaches are correct.

IV. BARN-POLE PARADOX

A. Description

One of the most well-known thought experiments illustrating the relativity of simultaneity is **the barn-pole paradox**. In this scenario, a pole at rest is longer than a barn, making it impossible to fit inside[14]. However, if the pole moves at a velocity close to the speed of light relative to the barn, relativistic length contraction reduces its length in the barn's frame, potentially allowing both barn doors to be closed simultaneously while the pole is entirely inside. From the perspective of the pole's reference frame, it is the barn that undergoes length contraction, appearing even shorter, so it seems impossible for the pole to fit. The paradox is resolved by recognizing that **simultaneity is relative**[15, p. 13]: events that are simultaneous in the barn's frame are not simultaneous in the pole's frame, which reconciles the apparent contradiction. This is also illustrated by the Minkowski diagram(Figure 8).

B. Analysis

FIG. 8: Minkowski diagram for the Barn-Pole paradox (Barn frame, S). The green line shows the simultaneous closing of the doors E_A and E_B in S, capturing the pole (L_p) inside the barn (L_b). The dashed blue line (simultaneous in S') shows that for the pole, event E_B occurs much earlier than event E_A .

To be able to explain more formally from a mathematical point of view, it is necessary to introduce the proper

length, which is defined as the length measured in the reference frame of the object itself. In the garage reference system, it is possible to define points A and B as the start and end of the pole, which will be respectively:

$$x_{pA}(t) = vt \quad x_{pB}(t) = vt + L_p$$

Where v is the translational speed of the pole, in the $+x$ direction, while L_p is its length measured in the reference frame of the barn.

The proper length of the pole is $L_0 = \frac{L_p}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$. The positions of the two doors will be given by:

$$x_{bA}(t) = 0 \quad x_{bB}(t) = L_b$$

If $L_b > L_p$, then it is possible to completely contain the pole. If door A closes at $t = 0$, immediately after the back of the pole has entered the barn, and door B closes within a time $T_1 \leq \frac{1}{v}(L_b - L_p)$, then for t in the interval $0 \leq t \leq T_1$, the pole will be completely inside the barn from the point of view of frame S . [15, p. 14].

Figure 9a shows the scenario that unfolds.

To see what happens in the reference frame S' , Lorentz transformations are used (Eq.(1)):

$$x'_{pA} = 0 \quad x'_{pB} = \gamma L_p$$

These are the positions of the ends of the pole, which are also consistent with the definition of proper length.

In the garage's frame of reference, both doors close simultaneously at time T (that is, $t_{bA} = t_{bB} = T$). What, instead, is observed from the reference frame of the pole?

Applying the Lorentz transformations to the positions of the doors gives:

$$t'_{bA} = 0, \quad t'_{bB} = \gamma(L_b - vT)$$

Hence, the barn appears even shorter in the pole's frame.

By applying the Lorentz transformation for time, using the coordinates x_{bA} , x_{bB} , t_{bA} , and t_{bB} , the following results are obtained:

$$t'_{bA} = \gamma T, \quad t'_{bB} = \gamma \left(T - \frac{vL_b}{c^2} \right)$$

In reference to the pole, therefore, door B closes first and reopens before the pole can collide with the door. When the back of the pole passes door A, it closes and then reopens later. All of this is shown in Figure 9b.

The paradox is therefore resolved through the concept of the relativity of simultaneity: two different observers see events occurring at different time intervals. The doors closing simultaneously in S are not simultaneous in S' .

FIG. 9: The two scenarios of the pole-and-barn paradox as seen from the two reference frames. Images adapted from Wikipedia–Ladder Paradox [14].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, three of the most famous thought experiments concerning Special Relativity have been addressed: **the Twin Paradox**, **Muon Decay**, and **the Barn-pole Paradox**. It has been demonstrated that these scenarios, while counterintuitive, do not expose any internal logical contradictions within the theory. On the contrary, they serve as powerful illustrations of its fundamental principles.

The resolution of each apparent paradox relied on the rigorous application of specific relativistic concepts, demonstrating the theory's full consistency:

In the Twin Paradox, the **apparent symmetry** between observers was broken by acknowledging the role of **acceleration**. Unlike the stationary twin (Andrew), the traveling twin (Barney) does not occupy a single inertial frame. The quantitative analysis, conducted using both **proper time** calculations and the **relativistic Doppler effect** on exchanged signals, unequivocally confirmed that the traveling twin experiences a shorter elapsed proper time, thus aging less.

The analysis of Muon Decay highlighted the theory's perfect self-consistency. The arrival of muons at the Earth's surface despite their short lifetime is explained from two complementary perspectives: for an observer on Earth, the muon reaches the ground due to **time di-**

lating extending its lifetime ; for the muon itself, **length contraction** reduces the atmospheric distance it must travel.

Finally, the Barn-pole Paradox was resolved by demonstrating that its origin lies in the **relativity of simultaneity**. Events that appear simultaneous in the barn's reference frame are not simultaneous in the pole's reference frame.

By demonstrating how time dilation, length contraction, and the relativity of simultaneity work in concert, these paradoxes are not only resolved without contradiction but also reveal a deeper, physically verified description of reality, thereby reinforcing the revolutionary validity of **Einstein's 1905 theory**.

VI. APPENDIX

A. Derivations of the Lorentz transformations

This section will cover the derivation of the Lorentz transformations with reference to two inertial systems translating along a single coordinate [16].

Consider two inertial reference systems moving with uniform rectilinear motion relative to each other along the x-axis, with the y and z axes parallel.

The relative velocity between the frames is v , with the initial condition that the origins of the two frames coincide at $t = t' = 0$.

1. **General form:** The most general form of a transformation between two RFs which preserves the uniformity of rectilinear motion is:

$$\begin{cases} x' = a_{11}x + a_{12}y + a_{13}z + a_{14}t \\ y' = a_{21}x + a_{22}y + a_{23}z + a_{24}t \\ z' = a_{31}x + a_{32}y + a_{33}z + a_{34}t \\ t' = a_{41}x + a_{42}y + a_{43}z + a_{44}t \end{cases}$$

2. **Use of assumptions:** Since the motion occurs only along the x direction, y' and z' do not depend on t or on other coordinates; similarly, x' and t' depends only on x and t .

$$\begin{cases} x' = a_{11}x + a_{14}t \\ y' = a_{22}y \\ z' = a_{33}z \\ t' = a_{41}x + a_{44}t \end{cases}$$

3. **Isotropy of space:** $a_{33} = a_{22}$.

4. **Coefficients depend on v :**

$$\begin{cases} x' = A(v)x + B(v)t \\ y' = E(v)y \\ z' = E(v)z \\ t' = D(v)x + C(v)t \end{cases}$$

5. **O' movement in O:** For the origin of O' , $x' = 0$. From the RF of O , it moves as $x = vt$.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 = Ax + Bt &\implies x = -\frac{B}{A}t \implies v = -\frac{B}{A} \\ &\implies B = -Av \end{aligned}$$

6. **If $v=0$:**

$$\begin{cases} x' = x \\ y' = y \\ z' = z \\ t' = t \end{cases}$$

$$A(0) = C(0) = E(0) = 1; D(0) = 0$$

7. **The spacetime interval is invariant:**

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - c^2t^2 = x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2 - c^2t'^2$$

8. **Apply invariance of the spacetime interval:** Substitute the linear forms $x' = Ax + Bt$, $y' = Ey$, $z' = Ez$ and $t' = Dx + Ct$ into the invariance condition:

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - c^2t^2 = A^2(x-vt)^2 + E^2y^2 + E^2z^2 - c^2(Ct+Dx)^2$$

9. **Principle of identity of polynomials:** By carrying out the calculations and applying the principle of identity of polynomials, the following relationships are obtained:

$$\begin{cases} A^2 - c^2D^2 = 1 \\ E^2 = 1 \\ A^2v^2 - c^2C^2 = -c^2 \\ vA^2 + c^2CD = 0 \end{cases}$$

10. **Solve for coefficients:** From the second equation and the fact that $E(0) = 1 \implies E = 1$

From the third equation:

$$A^2 = \frac{c^2}{v^2}(C^2 - 1) \quad (*^1)$$

Start from the first equation:

$$A^2 - c^2D^2 = 1$$

and substitute $A^2 = \frac{c^2}{v^2}(C^2 - 1)$:

$$C^2 - 1 - v^2D^2 = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \quad (*^2)$$

Substitute A^2 in the fourth equation:

$$v \frac{v^2}{c^2}(C^2 - 1) + c^2CD = 0 \implies D = \frac{1 - C^2}{vC}$$

Substitute D in $(*^2)$ and expand obtaining $C = \gamma$

- 11. **Determine A using C in (*1):** $A = \gamma$
- 12. **Determine B from $B = -Av$:** $B = v\gamma$
- 13. **Determine D from $D = \frac{1-C^2}{vC}$:** $D = -\frac{v}{c^2}\gamma$
- 14. **Final Lorentz transformations:** Substitute the coefficients into the linear transformations:

$$\begin{cases} x' = \gamma(x - vt) \\ y' = y \\ z' = z \\ t' = \gamma\left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases}$$

- 15. **Conclusion:** These are the Lorentz transformations for motion along the x -axis, derived from the assumptions of linearity, isotropy and invariance of the spacetime interval.

B. In-depth analysis of Minkowski space

1. *Einstein summation convention*

In the context of relativity, in many equations the summation symbol (\sum) appears, making the reading cumbersome. For this reason, Einstein summation convention, which eliminates the writing of summations through rules on indices, is very common.

For example, the application of a linear transformation to a vector can be written in the following way:

$$\vec{u} = A\vec{v} \implies u_i = \sum_{j=1}^n A_{ij}v_j$$

Using the convention, it would be written like this:

$$u_i = A_{ij}v_j$$

However, it is necessary to introduce rules that allow calculations with indices to be performed correctly [17].

- 1. When an index appears twice in a single term, a summation over all possible values of that index is implied.
- 2. Each index can appear at most twice in any term.
- 3. Each term must contain identical non-repeated indices.

In spacetime (hyperbolic), the meaning of superscript and subscript indices is important [18, p. 2]. The meaning of an index being up or down will be discussed properly in the following Appendix section (VIB2). In SR, for instance, The application of Lorentz transformations is often seen in SR, and it can be written compactly in this way:

$$x'^{\mu} = \Lambda_{\nu}^{\mu}x^{\nu} \implies x'^{\mu} = \Lambda_0^{\mu}x^0 + \Lambda_1^{\mu}x^1 + \Lambda_2^{\mu}x^2 + \Lambda_3^{\mu}x^3$$

It is crucial to remember about index notation that the indices are arbitrary symbols, and do not represent specific numbers. Repeated indices are called dummy indices and can be replaced with anything not yet used and different from the free indices, which must be the same on both sides of the equation.

2. *Covariant and contravariant tensors*

In the theory of relativity, tensors are the fundamental objects necessary for formulating the equations that describe reality. In this paragraph, a more detailed mathematical analysis on this topic will be carried out [19]. The Einstein summation convention is used.

Definition 1. *Tensors: In an m -dimensional space, a tensor of rank n is a mathematical object that has n indices, m^n components and obeys transformation rules.*

Examples (in 4-dimensional space):

Scalar \rightarrow Tensor of rank 0, $4^0 = 1$ component

Vector \rightarrow Tensor of rank 1, $4^1 = 4$ components

Matrix \rightarrow Tensor of rank 2, $4^2 = 16$ components

Definition 2. *A tensor is an object that is invariant under a change of coordinate systems, with its components that transform according to a special set of mathematical formulae.*

Theorem 1. *Suppose L is a coordinate transformation operator applied to a tensor:*

- Magnitude of tensor component will transform according to L

- Basis vector will transform according to L^{-1}

Definition 3. *Contravariant and covariant Tensors:*

Suppose L is a coordinate transformation operator applied to a tensor: A tensor whose components transform in a contravariant fashion is a contravariant tensor (with L). Contravariant components are specified using superscripts ($x^{\mu} = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3)$).

A tensor whose components transform in a covariant fashion is a covariant tensor (with L^{-1}). Covariant components are specified using subscripts ($x_{\nu} = (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3)$).

Definition 4. *Contravariant vector:*

The vector field V is said to be a contravariant tensor of rank 1 if its components v^i in the (x^i) -coordinate system and v'^i in the (x'^i) -coordinate system are related by the following law of transformation:

$$v'^i = v^r \frac{\partial x'^i}{\partial x^r}$$

Definition 5. *Covariant vector:*

The vector field U is said to be a covariant tensor of rank 1 if its components u_i in the (x^i) -coordinate system and u'_i in the (x'^i) -coordinate system are related by the following law of transformation:

$$u'_i = u_r \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial x'^i}$$

Theorem 2. If the inner product $E \equiv v^j u_j$ is defined in each coordinate system, it is an invariant. It does not change under changes of coordinates.

This section will not delve into the relationship between dual vectors and covariant components, but they are closely related to each other.

Definition 6. Metric Tensor:

The metric tensor is defined as:

$$g_{ij} = e_i \cdot e_j$$

The metric tensor can be used in order to raise or lower the indices, as in Eq.(4).

Definition 7. Metric Tensor Properties:

Suppose g is a matrix field, then to be a metric tensor:

1. The components g_{ij} are at least twice-differentiable
2. $g_{ij} = g_{ji}$
3. g is a bilinear form
4. $g_{ij} v^i v^j \neq \vec{0}$, unless $\vec{v} = \vec{0}$

Definition 8. Contravariant vector(rank 2):

A matrix field V is said to be a contravariant tensor of rank 2 if its components v^{ij} in the (x^i) -coordinate system and v'^{ij} in the (x'^i) -coordinate system are related by the following law of transformation:

$$v'^{ij} = v^{rs} \frac{\partial x'^i}{\partial x^r} \frac{\partial x'^j}{\partial x^s}$$

Definition 9. Covariant tensor(rank 2):

The vector field U is said to be a covariant tensor of rank 2 if its components u_{ij} in the (x^i) -coordinate system and u'_{ij} in the (x'^i) -coordinate system are related by the following law of transformation:

$$u'_{ij} = u_{rs} \frac{\partial x^r}{\partial x'^i} \frac{\partial x^s}{\partial x'^j}$$

Definition 10. Mixed tensor(rank 2):

The vector field Z is said to be a mixed tensor of rank 2 if its components z_j^i in the (x^i) -coordinate system and $z_j'^i$ in the (x'^i) -coordinate system are related by the following law of transformation:

$$z_j'^i = z_s^r \frac{\partial x'^i}{\partial x^r} \frac{\partial x^s}{\partial x'^j}$$

For higher-rank tensors, the definition is similar, with the addition of more terms and indices.

Definition 11. Contraction:

Suppose S a (p,q) tensor. The contraction of S with respect to a contravariant index i_f and a covariant index j_g is given by setting $i_f = j_g = u$ and evaluating the new tensor S' . S' is now a $(p-1,q-1)$ tensor.

Definition 12. Inner product:

Suppose S a (p,q) tensor and T a (r,s) tensor. Choose a contravariant index on $S(i_f)$ and a covariant index on $T(l_g)$. Let $i_f = j_g = u$. $S \cdot T$ is a tensor of rank $m = p + r + q + s - 2$.

Theorem 3. Quotient law for tensors:

Suppose S a (p,q) tensor. Suppose that:

$T_{j_1 j_2 \dots j_q}^{i_1 i_2 \dots i_p} V^k \equiv S$. Then, T is a tensor with rank $(p, q+1)$.

C. Hyperbolic rotations

Consider a boost along the x-axis. In Euclidean geometry, distances are preserved, which can be expressed as $(ct)^2 + x^2 = r^2$, with r a constant. In a Cartesian graph it would represent a circle. As for Minkowski space, what is preserved is $(ct)^2 - x^2$, which graphically is a hyperbola. Lorentz boost can therefore be seen as a **hyperbolic rotation** in space (ct, x) . In fact, starting from:

$$\begin{cases} x' = \gamma(x - vt) \\ t' = \gamma\left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases}$$

the system can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{cases} x' = \gamma(x - \beta ct) \\ ct' = \gamma(ct - \beta x) \end{cases}$$

At this point, a new parameter, rapidity, is defined, such that:

$$\tanh(\phi) = \beta = \frac{v}{c}$$

From which the following relationships are obtained:

$$\cosh(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \tanh(\phi)^2}} = \gamma$$

$$\sinh(\phi) = \tanh(\phi) \cosh(\phi) = \beta \gamma$$

Now it is possible to rewrite the transformations in this way:

$$\begin{cases} x' = x \cosh(\phi) - ct \sinh(\phi) \\ ct' = -x \sinh(\phi) + ct \cosh(\phi) \end{cases}$$

The spacetime interval in S' is computed as:

$$(ct')^2 - (x')^2 = (-x \sinh \phi + ct \cosh \phi)^2 - (x \cosh \phi - ct \sinh \phi)^2$$

After expanding the squares:

$$\begin{aligned} (ct')^2 - (x')^2 &= x^2(\sinh^2 \phi - \cosh^2 \phi) + (ct)^2(\cosh^2 \phi - \sinh^2 \phi) \\ &\quad + 2x(ct)(-\sinh \phi \cosh \phi + \sinh \phi \cosh \phi) \end{aligned}$$

The cross terms cancel, and by applying the hyperbolic identity

$$\cosh^2 \phi - \sinh^2 \phi = 1,$$

it follows that:

$$(ct')^2 - (x')^2 = (ct)^2 - x^2.$$

The Minkowski interval is invariant under Lorentz transformations.

D. Principle of causality in SR

In principle, the relativity of simultaneity could also make the temporal order of events recorded by different inertial observers relative, a fact that could undermine the principle of causality governing the laws of physics [4, p. 74]. consider the Lorentz transformation related to time from S' to S written in interval form:

$$(t_2 - t_1) = \gamma[(t'_2 - t'_1) + \frac{v}{c^2}(x'_2 - x'_1)]$$

$$\implies (t_2 - t_1) = \gamma(t'_2 - t'_1)[1 + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{(x'_2 - x'_1)}{(t'_2 - t'_1)}]$$

If $(t'_2 - t'_1) > 0$, $(t_2 - t_1)$ can be negative if $[1 + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{(x'_2 - x'_1)}{(t'_2 - t'_1)}]$.

It follows that in the theory of special relativity, the temporal order of events is relative. All of this can threaten **the principle of causality**, which states:

-The event that precedes (cause) uniquely determines the event that follows (effect) by means of some physical action;

-the cause-effect relationship is absolute and verified by every observer.

The principle of causality requires that the temporal order of events in a causal relationship be absolute. It is necessary to impose positivity on the quantity in square brackets:

$$1 + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{(x'_2 - x'_1)}{(t'_2 - t'_1)} \leq 1 + \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{|x'_2 - x'_1|}{|t'_2 - t'_1|}$$

This leads to the following result:

$$|x'_2 - x'_1| \leq c|t'_2 - t'_1|$$

Lorentz transformations state that, in general, the temporal order of events is relative. However, when such events are in a potential causal relationship, their temporal order becomes absolute and is the same in all inertial references. Another important conclusion that can be drawn is the fact that in the theory of special relativity, **causality is local**.

E. Derivation of the Doppler effect

In this appendix, the relativistic Doppler effect is derived by using geometric arguments consistent with Lorentz transformations, showing the equivalence with the classical formula for longitudinal motion.

Suppose an observer S sees light from a source in S' moving away at velocity v [20].

FIG. 10: (a) When a light wave is emitted by a source fixed in the moving inertial frame S' , the observer in S sees the wavelength measured in S' to be shorter by a factor $\frac{1}{\gamma}$. (b) Because the observer sees the source moving away within S , the wave pattern reaching the observer in S is also stretched by the factor $(1 + \frac{v}{c})$.

Images and caption adapted from LibreTexts Physics-Doppler Effect for Light.[20]

The wavelength of the light could be measured within $S'(\lambda')$ and calculated in S through the contraction of lengths: $\lambda = \frac{\lambda'}{\gamma}$. It must also be considered that the observer in S observes a stretched wave due to the fact that S' is in motion(Figure 10). The stretching factor will be:

$$\frac{c\Delta t + v\Delta t}{c\Delta t} = (1 + \frac{v}{c})$$

Thus, considering both effects:

$$\lambda = \lambda'(1 + \frac{v}{c})\gamma \implies \lambda = \lambda' \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}}$$

In terms of frequency, using $c = \lambda\nu$, the following result is obtained:

$$\nu = \nu' \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v}{c}}}$$

Approaching, the velocity sign reverses:

$$\nu = \nu' \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}}$$

An alternative and more compact derivation of the relativistic Doppler effect can be obtained by introducing the **wave four-vector**

$$k^\mu = \left(\frac{\omega}{c}, \mathbf{k}\right),$$

which transforms under a Lorentz boost as

$$k'^{\mu} = \Lambda^{\mu}_{\nu} k^{\nu}.$$

Since the **phase of the wave** is a Lorentz invariant,

$$k_{\mu} x^{\mu} = k'_{\mu} x'^{\mu},$$

it follows that the frequency and wavenumber components are related by the same transformation laws as time

and space. For a boost along the x -axis,

$$\begin{cases} k'_x = \gamma \left(k_x - \frac{v\omega}{c^2} \right) \\ \omega' = \gamma (\omega - vk_x) \end{cases}$$

and, using $k_x = \omega/c$ for light in vacuum, the following result is obtained:

$$\frac{\omega'}{\omega} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta}}$$

This expression is identical to the one previously derived geometrically, showing that the **relativistic Doppler effect** is a direct consequence of the Lorentz transformation properties of the wave four-vector.

- [1] Robert Resnick. *Introduction to Special Relativity*. John Wiley, New York, 1968.
- [2] A. Einstein. On the electrodynamics of moving bodies. *Annalen der Physik*, 1905.
- [3] Various Authors. *Hundert Autoren gegen Einstein*. Verlag Reiss, Leipzig, 1931.
- [4] Nicola Semprini Cesari. Appunti di relatività speciale (teoria). Lecture notes, Università di Bologna, 2024.
- [5] H. Lorentz. Electromagnetic phenomena in a system moving with any velocity whatever less than that of light. *Proceedings of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences.*, 1904.
- [6] Hermann Minkowski. Raum und zeit. *Jahresbericht der Deutschen Mathematiker-Vereinigung*, 1908.
- [7] Y.A. Ramachers. Lecture notes px421: Relativity and electrodynamics. https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/physics/staff/academic/ramachers/px421_main.pdf, 2014.
- [8] Jean-Marc Lévy-Leblond. Additivity, rapidity, relativity. <https://dspace.ut.ee/server/api/core/bitstreams/4495c3e3-82f3-45de-9c01-fc358a4fad9e/content>, 1978.
- [9] Francesco Ravanini. Appunti di relatività ristretta. <https://www.bo.infn.it/~ravanini/relativity/Ristretta.pdf>, 2007.
- [10] Zanko Ventsislavov Mezdrichki. Twin paradox plot. <https://github.com/zanko-mezdrichki/twin-paradox-plot>.
- [11] B. Rossi and D. B. Hall. Variation of the rate of decay of mesotrons with momentum. *Physical Review*, Vol. 59, 1941.
- [12] Particle Data Group. Review of Particle Physics. <https://pdglive.lbl.gov/Particle.action?node=S004>, 2025.
- [13] MIT. Relativity notes, 32nd lecture summary. https://www.atmosp.physics.utoronto.ca/people/strong/phy140/lecture32_01.pdf, 2025.
- [14] Wikipedia contributors. Ladder paradox. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ladder_paradox.
- [15] Ying-Qiu Gu. Some paradoxes in special relativity. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0902.2032>, 2009.
- [16] Alessandro Catania. Trasformazioni di lorentz. <https://www.youmath.it/lezioni/fisica/teoria-della-relativita-ristretta/3418-trasformazioni-di-lorentz.html>.
- [17] Christopher Stover and Eric W. Weisstein. Einstein summation. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/EinsteinSummation.html>.
- [18] lmu.build. Notes on Index Notation PHYS 471. <https://www.jmureika.lmu.build/PHYS471/InClass/IndexNotation.pdf>.
- [19] Faculty of Khan. Tensor Calculus. https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLdgvB0aXkb9D6zw47gsrtE5XqLerPh27_.
- [20] LibreTexts-Physics. 5.8: Doppler effect for light. [https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/University_Physics/University_Physics_\(OpenStax\)/University_Physics_III_-_Optics_and_Modern_Physics_\(OpenStax\)/05%3A_Relativity/5.08%3A_Doppler_Effect_for_Light](https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/University_Physics/University_Physics_(OpenStax)/University_Physics_III_-_Optics_and_Modern_Physics_(OpenStax)/05%3A_Relativity/5.08%3A_Doppler_Effect_for_Light).